

Supplementary Materials

Nyquist Plot of experimental Impedance data

The experimental impedance data on which the analysis is based are shown in Figure S-1, Figure S-2 and Figure S-3.

Figure S-1. Nyquist plot of experimental impedance data in function of different pressure and temperature at different potentials (0.8V (a), 0.7V (b), 0.6V (c), 0.5V (d) and 0.4V (e)) at 100% RH.

Figure S-2. Nyquist plot of experimental impedance data at different flow rates and voltage: 0.8V (a), 0.7V (b), 0.6V (c), 0.5V (d) and 0.4V (e).

Figure S-3. Nyquist plot of experimental impedance data with air and oxygen at: 0.8V (a), 0.7V (b), 0.6V (c), 0.5V (d) and 0.4V (e) with 70°C, 0.5 bar and 100% RH.

Statistical Analysis: Regression 3-D plot.

The 3D plots of the nonlinear regression on the resistances as a function of current density, pressure, and temperature are shown in Figure S-4.

Figure S-4. Regression surface for ohmic resistance and P1-P5 peaks resistance.